

PSYCHOANALYTICAL FEATURES OF “ALCHEMIST”

BY PAOLO COELHO

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ABSTRACT

This thesis states information about psychoanalytical method and its use in “ Alchemist “ by Paolo Coelho. Interrelationship between psychology and literature are exposed in this thesis. Psychologists who emphasize inner world of characters in their works,

Key words: psychology, psychoanalytic method, Muslims religious background, Santiago , Egypt, destination, feelings, sensations

Psychologism in literature is the transfer by the author to the reader of the inner world of his characters. Other types of art also have the ability to convey sensations and feelings. But literature, thanks to its imagery, has the ability to depict the state of mind of a person to the smallest detail. The author, trying to describe the hero, gives details of his appearance, the interior of the room. Often in the literature, a technique such as a landscape is used to convey the psychological state of characters.[]

Psychoanalytic criticism adopts the methods of "reading" employed by Sigmund Freud and later theorists to interpret texts. It argues that literary texts, like dreams, express the secret unconscious desires and anxieties of the author, that a literary work is a manifestation of the author's own neuroses. One may psychoanalyze a particular character within a literary work, but it is usually assumed that all such characters are projections of the author's psyche.

One interesting fact of this approach is that it validates the importance of literature, as it is built on a literary key for the decoding. Freud himself wrote, "The dream-thoughts which we first come across as we proceed with our analysis often strike us by the unusual form in which they are expressed; they are not clothed in the prosaic language usually employed by our thoughts, but are on the contrary represented symbolically by means of similes and metaphors, in images resembling those of poetic speech" . Like psychoanalysis itself, this critical endeavor seeks evidence of unresolved emotions, psychological conflicts, guilts, ambivalences, and so forth within what may well be a disunified literary work. The author's own childhood traumas, family life, fixations, and such will be traceable within the behavior of the characters in the literary work. But psychological material will be expressed indirectly, disguised, or encoded through principles such as "symbolism" , "condensation" , and "displacement". [2]

Literature psychology means "the effects of literature upon its readers or audience psychology". The correlation between psychology and literature is strong as literature could have an influence to the reader's feeling and personality. The reason is to aim writing as a literary work of psychological opinions about the life and writers who make a novel or story. Through this, authors can give motivation and support to thereaders till their feelings get better.

"Alchemist" by Paolo Coelho. It can be said that the whole work connects with psychology. The story is all about Santiago who travels cross many countries till he reaches his destination which is Egypt aiming to find treasure, while facing a lot of struggles that could not stop him from continuing to follow his dream. When Santiago faced any difficulties, every time he discovered new essence and value of life for himself.

In literary work, writer must state characters mood , and behavior create clear picture in their mind. This demands from writers or authors to have some knowledge on psychology to describe effectively characters situations climate, and athmosphere of the work. There is strong correlation between psychology and literature. Because both

of them deal with people's emotion , fear, wish, desire, perception and etc. Having read this book, you can turn positively your mental and behavioral characters. For instance:

-The novel has a strong religious background, Muslim readers would feel that their religion is supported by some ideas were written in the novel. According to the novel the whole universe would conspire to support your dream , And the same concept was mentioned in the Quran.

-The overall experience and moral are incredibly inspiring the reader to find the light in a dark path.

-The novel leaves a positive impact in the reader mind, after reaching the end it influences the reader perspective of life.

-The words and the ideas were suitable for everyone, in different ages.

-Multiple Religious perspective, the novel mentioned that there is one god, but everyone interprets differently, this explanation is a descent simplification for different religions idea which help the reader to be more open minded and acceptable.

-Humanity has commonalities, which reduced the cultural and religious gap between different characters in the novel

-The writer simple manner of storytelling allows the reader to discern deeper meaning from what he is saying.

But some researchers' point of views, it is not true to say just benefits of the work, drawbacks are also not disclaimed in the work. For instance:

Alchemist novel is imaginary. However, the strong meaningful ideas the novels represent but it is not realistic. The reasons why He started this journey till the end , was not real enough for readers to imagine.

The novel main ideas were not easily to understand, it could be considered as wisdom as well as it could cause a confusion to the reader due to the mixed thoughts and beliefs.

The only female character in the novel was Fatima, However, the novel was about equality and acceptance women role was not an interesting idea for Coelho, which disagree with the overall idea.[3]

Here are given some impressive phrases from the work:

But in his heart he knew that it did matter. And he knew that shepherds, like seamen and like traveling salesmen, always found a town where there was someone who could make them forget the joys of carefree wandering.

As Santiago muses about the Moorish girl he has met, he makes the first of many connections between his own Personal Legend, or destiny, and that of many others. Santiago recognizes that his unique narrative follows a pattern he has seen before in the lives of itinerant workers. He draws the conclusion that the love of another can outweigh the loss of freedom. Santiago derives support from placing the personal into a universal context.

It's the possibility of having a dream come true that makes life interesting, he thought, as he looked again at the position of the sun, and hurried his pace.

Santiago reflects on what it means to travel and discover. Early in the novel, wanderlust combined with his attraction to the merchant's daughter begin to take hold of his soul. His Personal Legend is at the point of departure. The sun's course in the sky marks the passage of time, and Santiago feels the anxious anticipation of arriving at his destination.

If someone isn't what others want them to be, the others become angry. Everyone seems to have a clear idea of how other people should lead their lives, but none about his or her own.

Santiago muses about how people judge others' choices in life, recalling the opposition he experienced in the seminary. The people who were part of his life wanted him to change and he compared their ideas for him with their own choices. He resisted such pressure by leaving the settled seminary existence and choosing an itinerant lifestyle [4].

Conclusion. To sum up, Coelho is the writer of the alchemist novel which based on the psychological analysis. The main idea about a guy named Santiago who started his journey from Indonesia to Egypt to find treasure, no matter what he faces through his journey the spirit inside him never fade. The moral is to inspire millions of readers, motivate them, offer different aspect of life and use humanity as a common language despite different cultures.

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